

**Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central
Co-operative Society Limited
- A Study on the Perception of Customers**

Ninikala K. *

Dr. B. Johnson **

Abstract

The success of a product depends on the ability of the organisation in providing adequate, timely and reliable information to the prospective customers. Every organisation develops its own marketing strategies in attracting the different strata of customers. KDBWCCS has different types of products and developed its own distribution system. The customers' awareness about different products manufactured by the Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers' Central Society is important. It is because they are producing wide variety of products. Dinesh food unit produces curry powders, pickles, Kera milk, squash, jam and so on. Dinesh umbrella unit produces different types of umbrella for ladies, gents and kids. And finally Dinesh garments also make various types of dresses for ladies, gents, kids and also home textiles. The central co-operative society must take steps to make aware of their customers about the different products and encourage them to use these products again and again. This article attempts to find out the perception of customers about the diversified products of the Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central Co-operative Society.

Key words : Customer services, Demand, Price, Promotional offers and Quality.

Introduction

In 1969, an important experiment in industrial democracy happened around the city of Kannur in the name of Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central Cooperative Society. Kerala Dinesh Beedi workers manufactured beedies, or poor people's cigarettes. Their main work was rolling beedies, which engaged 95% of the work force. At that time 3000 workers were employed in 20 Primary Societies which were located in three districts namely Kasargode, Kannur and Kozhikode. Later the government banned smoking at public place and that affected the beedi manufacturers a lot. Kerala Dinesh Beedi (KDB), the largest beedi manufacturing company in the corporate sector, registered a turnover of Rs. 70 crores at that time was not able maintain its production level as the sales declined. KDB has recorded

**Guest lecturer, St. Joseph's College, Devagiri, Kozhikode*

***Associate Professor, Department of Commerce and Management Studies, University of Calicut- 673 635.*

a steep fall (over 30%) in sales during that period and production stands affected due to poor take by agents within the state and outside. This affected the existence of the society. KDB has conducted extensive research into the possibilities of shifting into agro-processing. The society decided to shift 25% of the workers into nontobacco production over the next 10 years.

The mission of the Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central Co-operative Society [KDBWCCS] is the upliftment of weaker sections in the society; which is focusing on new ventures to create more employments. It started a coconut milk extraction unit during 1997, curry powder and pickle unit during 1998 and a fruit processing unit during 1999 and also started more labour oriented umbrella assembling unit during 2000. Dinesh Information Technology system (DITS) is the IT unit of KDBWCCS, started in 1999 with state of art facilities namely Dinesh Software Park, well suited for software development, Business processing and outsourcing and training centres. Dinesh Garments is a new venture setup in 2007 with advanced technology to produce export quality products.

Dinesh Foods

Dinesh Food is a Division of Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers' Central Co-op Society and is functioning since 1998 as the first unit under diversification programme. The unit is located at Thottada, Kannur District. Under Food division there are two manufacturing units: Curry Powder and pickle unit and Fruit Processing. Various products produced by Dinesh Foods are Coconut milk extraction (Kera milk), Pickle, Curry Powder, Pappadam, Tea Product, Jams, Squash and Syrups.

Marketing Strategy: The Dinesh Food Products are sold through a wide network of authorized distributors, who supply to wholesalers and retailers throughout Kerala. About 65% of Dinesh Food Products are sold through authorized distributors, 25% through institutional buyers and 10% to direct consumers. Their institutional buyers are: Kerala Civil Supplies Corporation, Consumer Fed, Indian Coffee Houses and Co-operative stores.

Quality Control: Stringent quality control system is in place to make every product perfectly safe. HACCP (Hazard Analysis Critical Control Point) to ensure 100% food safety is under implementation. Fruit processing division is working in tune with Govt. of India FPI guidelines and the products are FPO certified. Kera Milk is processed under scientific support and guidance from Regional Research Lab, Govt. of India.

Dinesh Umbrella

Dinesh Umbrella is a division of Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central Co-op: Society Ltd. It was started as diversification programme in 2000. It has two

umbrella production centres one in Kannur (Chalad) and other in Thalassery. Dinesh Umbrella is one of the popular brands in Kerala especially among Co-Operate Institutions, Banks etc. Each umbrella is made out of best quality parts imported from Korea, Japan, Taiwan etc. The frames are rustproof, the cover panels are nylon silver coated and the handles are most attractive. Each piece is tested for high quality in the factory by expert in the field. They manufacture different types of umbrella such as gents special, Ladies Special and Children Special

Marketing Strategy : The Dinesh Umbrella's are sold through a wide network of authorized distributors, who supply to wholesalers and retailers throughout Kerala. About 65% of Dinesh Umbrella is sold through authorized distributors, 25% through institutional buyers and 10% to direct consumers. Their institutional buyers are: Co-operative Banks, Co- Op: institutions, Govt. Institutions, Govt. Departments, Vismaya Park, Parassinikkadavu, and Leading Gold Jewellers – Malabar Gold.

Dinesh Garments

Dinesh Garments is the latest unit of diversification programmes of Dinesh Beedi Central Co-operative society. It started its operations from the year 2007, at Kannur Districts as a part of G.K Panicker Memorial Auditorium. It produces wide ranges of Men's shirt, ladies wear, Home textiles etc. In the year 2009-10, they started their export promotion under the strict order of material. Their second Apparel unit was inaugurated by the former Industries Minister Elamaram Karim at Chala, Kannur on 4th June 2010.

Quality : They have ISO 9001-2008 certificates under International Quality. Now a work could be associated to get SA 8000 a special certificate and also got approval for using silk materials from central silk board that has the authority to certify natural silk quality. 100% of employees are women and all the technical staffs are well trained in doing any type of garmenting work. Its operations started in 2007 and product range includes mainly export varieties meant for US & European markets.

Research Problem

The society started their diversification programme since 1997. KDBWCCS has different types of products and it has developed its own distribution system. Even after 14 years from their diversification still their products are not much known to the public. There is a need to know why the product is not attractive among the customers. The success of a product depends on the ability of the organisation in providing adequate, timely and reliable information to the prospective customers. The customers' awareness about different products manufactured by the Central Society is important. There is a need to analyse the manner in which customers perceive the diversified products of Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central Co-operative Society.

Significance of the Study

The present paper deals with customers' perception about the diversified products of Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central Co-operative Society (KDBWCCS). Government had granted Rs.4 crore to the Central Society for the purpose of diversification programme undertaken by them. Using these funds the society gave birth to different products such as food items, umbrella garments, software and soaps and chemicals. In order to identify the effectiveness of these products, there is a need to know the response of the customers. Based on the responses of the customers, the society may be able to bring the required policies which will satisfy the expectations of the customers.

Scope of the Study

The study deals with diversification programme undertaken by Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Central Co-operative Society (KDBWCCS). The scope of the study is limited to only three units of the society. They are Dinesh Garments, Dinesh Foods and Dinesh Umbrella, as they are the leading diversified units of the Central Co-operative Society. The study mainly focuses on customers of the three units.

Review of Literature

Many studies have been conducted about operational activities of Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Cooperative Society. Details of important studies are depicted here.

Praveesh M (2010) in his study entitled 'Analysis of Financial Performance of Dinesh Foods' was conducted to evaluate the overall financial performance of Dinesh Foods. The study reveals that liquidity position of the company was not good and they were not able to maintain ideal ratio. Working capital of the company was utilised in an apt manner and the share holder also got satisfactory return on their investment. It was concluded that by taking necessary steps to reduce the cost of production and by making efficient inventory management system, the company can increase the profit.

Larish K.C (2011) in his study entitled 'the attitude and preference of retailers and end users of Dinesh Food Products' examined about the attitude of retailers and end users regarding processed food products. Samples of 150 respondents from Kannur District were selected for the study which includes 50 retailers and 100 end users. Simple Random Sampling method was used to select samples. The study reveals that most of the retailer's deals with other fast moving brands because the promotional campaigns undertaken were only average and other products have good advertisement support. Even then the retailers are satisfied with the credit period and delivery system. Among the customers it was found that curry powders are having more demand and only an average number of cus-

tomers were aware about the products. It was concluded that non availability of the product and lack of promotional activities were the main drawbacks of the society.

Anoop C.M (2011) in his study entitled 'Consumer awareness and market potentiality of Dinesh Food Products with respect to Kannur District' studied the market potentials of Kerala Dinesh Food Products and to know about consumer awareness level. It was found that only a few customers are aware about Dinesh Brands and Dinesh Food Products. Selected customers get information about the Dinesh products only through their friends and relatives. The major reasons for the success of the product were its quality and reasonable price.

Objectives of the Study

1. To evaluate the quality of the products of three units viz. food, umbrella and garments.
2. To assess the effectiveness of price of different products of the central cooperative society
3. To identify major factors influencing the vis-a-vis approach of the product.

Hypotheses

1. There is no difference in the perception of customers with regard to the quality of products of three units.
2. There is no difference in the opinion of customers with regard to the prices of Dinesh products.
3. The promotional offers provided for the different dinesh products are the same
4. Customers have the same opinion about the three different dinesh products

Research Methodology and Data Base

The present study has been designed as a descriptive one based on both primary data and secondary data. The secondary data, for the study has been collected from various sources viz. byelaw of the central cooperative society, annual reports published by the society, journals, magazines and websites of KDB. Since most of the information necessary to fulfil the objectives of the study is not available from secondary data, the study is mainly based on primary data collected through a sample survey of customers of KDBWCCS using a structured and pre-tested interview schedule. Discussions were also made with officials and experts of all the three units namely Dinesh foods, Dinesh umbrella and Dinesh garments.

Sample Design

Three units of the society were taken for the study; Dinesh foods, Dinesh umbrella and Dinesh garments. For the purpose of collecting data, detailed list of customers of all the three units were availed from the central cooperative society. And from the total list of customers sample of 57 was drawn using simple random sampling method. Among them 15 samples were from the customers of Dinesh Garments, 18 from Dinesh Umbrella and 24 from Dinesh Foods.

Tools used for Data Collection

Field survey was conducted to collect primary data from the customers of KDBWCCS. A well structured interview schedule was developed for collecting data from customers of KDB. For the purpose of the study a pilot survey was conducted among the selected customers of diversified products of the society. On the basis of the experience of the pilot survey, the questions were revised and schedule was redrafted.

Tools for Data Analysis

- ◀ Percentage Analysis
- ◀ Chi square test
- ◀ Kruskal Wallis test

The results of the analysis of primary data collected are presented below.

1. Quality of Dinesh Products

Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers' Central Co-operative deals with different divisions such as Dinesh foods, Dinesh umbrella and Dinesh Garments. Each division produces different grades of products. The society gives much emphasis on the quality of the products. They are not ready to make any compromise in the quality of their products. However it is of paramount importance to identify the customers' response and reactions about the quality of Dinesh products. All the information collected from the customers with regard to the quality of Dinesh product sare analysed using Kruskal Wallis test. The result obtained is shown in the following table.

TABLE 1

RANKING OF CUSTOMERS RESPONSE ABOUT THE QUALITY USING KRUSKAL WALLIS TEST

<i>Products</i>	<i>Median</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Average Rank</i>	<i>d.f</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Food	1.00	24	24.27		
Umbrella	2.00	18	33.03		
Garments	2.00	15	31.73		
Total	2.00	57		2	0.1341

Source : Primary data

As per table, Median of Dinesh food is 1 and that of Dinesh umbrella and Dinesh garment is 2. N represents the sample size of each unit. 24 samples were drawn from Dinesh food, 18 from Dinesh umbrella and 15 from Dinesh garments. Average rank obtained in case of Dinesh food was 24.27, Dinesh umbrella was 33.03 and Dinesh garments was 31.73. P value obtained after analysing the data using Kruskal Wallis test at degrees of freedom 2 was .1341 Since the p value (.1341) is greater than .05, the null hypothesis: there is no significant difference in the perception of customers with regard to the quality of products can be accepted.

2. Prices of Dinesh Products

The central society is dealing with wide variety of products. Price is an important factor that influences the customers. In order to know customers opinion about the prices of Dinesh products data collected are analysed using Kruskal-Wallis test and the result obtained is shown in the table below.

TABLE 2
RESULT OF CUSTOMERS OPINION ABOUT
THE PRICES USING KRUSKAL WALLIS TEST

Products	Median	N	Average Rank	d.f	P-value
Food	2.00	24	22.44		
Umbrella	3.00	18	36.92		
Garments	3.00	15	30.00		
Total	3.00	57		2	.0083

Source : Primary data

Median obtained after analysis in case of Dinesh food is two and that of Dinesh umbrella and Dinesh garments are three. N represents sample size. The total samples drawn from the customers of all the three units were 57 which include 24 from Dinesh food, 18 from Dinesh umbrella and 15 from Dinesh garments. Average rank obtained in case of Dinesh food is 22.44, Dinesh umbrella is 36.92 and Dinesh garments is 30. P value obtained after analysis at degrees of freedom 2 is .0083. In order to test the whether there is any difference in the opinion of the customers with regard to their prices following hypothesis is formulated. As the p value (.0077) is less than .05, the null hypothesis: there is no significant difference in the opinion of customers with regard to the prices of Dinesh products is rejected. Hence it may be generalised that there is significant difference in the opinion of customers with regard to the prices of Dinesh products.

2. Demand for Dinesh Products

To identify the customers' opinion about the demand for Dinesh products the data collected are presented in the following table.

TABLE 3

DISTRIBUTION OF DEMAND FOR DINESH PRODUCTS

	Food		Umbrella		Garments		Total	
	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent
Very high	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
High	5	20.83	5	27.78	0	0.00	10	17.54
Moderate	9	37.50	9	50.00	9	60.00	27	47.37
Low	7	29.17	4	22.22	6	40.00	17	29.82
Very low	3	12.50	0	0.00	0	0.00	3	5.26
Total	24	100.00	18	100.00	15	100.00	57	100.00

Pearson Chi-square: 9.87721, df=6, p=.129959

Source : Primary data

Majority of the customers of Dinesh products were of the opinion that demand for Dinesh product was moderate. 37.50 per cent customers' of Dinesh foods, 50 per cent customers' of Dinesh umbrella and 47.37 per cent customers' of Dinesh Garments responded that demand for their product was moderate. Overall only 17.54 per cent customers were of the opinion that the demand for Dinesh product was high. As the p value obtained at degrees of freedom 6 using Chi square test was .1299599 which is greater than .05, so it can be said that the customers opinion about the demand for Dinesh products are same. It means there is no difference in the opinion of the customers of all the three units with regard to demand for Dinesh products

4. Rating of Promotional Offers

To promote the sales of Dinesh products, the central society have undertaken necessary measures. Following table reveals customers responses about the promotional offers provided by the society.

TABLE 4

DISTRIBUTION OF PROMOTIONAL OFFERS PROVIDED BY THE SOCIETY

Promotional Offers	Food		Umbrella		Garments		Total	
	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent
High	0	0.006	0	0.00	7	46.67	7	12.28
Average	14	58.33	11	61.11	8	53.33	33	57.89
Low	10	41.67	7	38.89	0	0.00	17	29.82
Total	24	100.00	18	100.00	15	100.00	57	100.00

Source : Primary data

Note : Pearson Chi-square 25.78, d.f.=4, p=0.000035

Majority of the customers of Dinesh products was of the opinion that promotional offers provided by the society were average. About 58.33 per cent customers of Dinesh Food, 61.11 per cent customers of Dinesh umbrella and 53.33 per cent customers of Dinesh Garments were of the opinion that promotional offers provided were only average. In order to test the hypothesis that: customers opinion about promotional offers provided by all the three units is same the P value .000035 is compared with .05. As the p value is less, the null hypothesis is rejected which means that the customers have different opinions about the promotional offers provided by the society in respect of the three products.

Rating of Customer Services

Each units of the central society is dealing with wide variety of products. They mainly focus on the customers and they aim the satisfaction of the customers. They render various services to their customers. The following table helps the society to know about customer's opinion about the services rendered by each unit.

TABLE 5

DISTRIBUTION OF CUSTOMERS' OPINION ABOUT SERVICES RENDERED BY THE SOCIETY

Customer Services	Food		Umbrella		Garments		Total	
	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent
Very good	5	20.83	2	11.11	3	20.00	10	17.54
Good	11	45.83	5	27.78	5	33.33	21	36.84
Average	4	16.67	8	44.44	7	46.67	19	33.33
Poor	3	12.50	3	16.67	0	0	6	10.53
Very Poor	1	4.17	0	0.00	0	0	1	1.76
Total	24	100.00	18	100.00	15	100.00	57	100.00

Source : Primary data

Pearson Chi-square:8.76 , df=8, p=0.3633

Majority of the customers of food units (45.83 per cent) opined that services rendered by them are good. But majority of customers of umbrella unit (44.44 per cent) and garments units (46.67 per cent) opined that services rendered by these units are only average. To test whether there is any difference in the opinion of the customers following hypothesis is formulated.

H₀ : There is no significant difference between the opinion of customers of food, umbrella and garments about the service rendered by the society.

To test the above hypothesis Chi-square test is used and p value obtained at degrees of freedom 8 is .3633, which is greater than .05. That means null hypothesis formulated is accepted.

5. Fulfilment of Needs and Expectation of Customers'

In the present market, products are produced according to the taste and preference of the customers. So it is necessary to know whether the customers are able to meet their needs and expectations with regard to the quality and performance of Dinesh products.

TABLE 6
DISTRIBUTION OF THE CUSTOMERS' OPINION ABOUT FULFILMENT OF THEIR NEEDS AND EXPECTATION

	Food		Umbrella		Garments		Total	
	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent
Yes	14	58.33	15	83.33	11	73.33	40	70.18
No	10	41.67	3	16.67	4	26.67	17	29.82
Total	24	100.00	18	100.00	15	100.00	57	100.00

Source : Primary data

Above table clearly reveals that overall 70.18 per cent customers were able to meet their needs and expectations with regard to the quality and performance of Dinesh products. Only 29.82 per cent customers of all the three units opined that they were not able to meet their needs and expectation.

6. Factors that Attracted the Customers

In between the two factors price and quality, which is more influencing with respect to the three products is being asked among the customers and the result obtained is tabulated in the following table.

TABLE 7
FACTORS THAT INFLUENCED THE CUSTOMERS

	Food		Umbrella		Garments		Total	
	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent
Price	5	20.83	6	33.33	9	60.00	20	35.09
Quality	19	79.17	12	66.67	6	40.00	37	64.91
Total	24	100.00	18	100.00	15	100.00	57	100.00

Source : Primary data

The main factors that influence the customers towards Dinesh product were its price and quality. Majority of the customers of Dinesh food (79.17 per cent) and Dinesh garments (66.67 per cent) opined that quality is the main factor that influenced them. But 60 per cent customers of Dinesh garments were of the

opinion that price was the main factor influenced them. Overall 64.91 per cent customer of all the three units together opined that quality is the main factor that influenced them.

7. Drawbacks of Dinesh Products

In order to examine the main drawback of Dinesh products which affected its popularity, the opinions of the selected customers were being obtained and the result of the same is presented in the following table.

TABLE 8
DRAWBACKS OF DINESH PRODUCTS

	Food		Umbrella		Garments		Total	
	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent
Lack of advertisement	19	79.17	11	61.11	8	53.33	38	66.67
High price	1	4.17	4	22.22	3	20.00	8	14.04
Lack of Knowledge of customers	2	8.33	1	5.56	2	13.33	5	8.77
Others	2	8.33	2	11.11	2	13.33	6	10.53
Total	24	100.00	18	100.00	15	100.00	57	100.00

Source : Primary data

From the above table it is clear that main drawbacks of Dinesh Products are lack of advertisements. Overall 66.67 per cent customers of all the three units together were of the opinion that lack of proper advertisements is the main drawback of Dinesh products, which include 79.17 per cent customers of Dinesh food, 61.11 per cent customers of Dinesh umbrella and 53.33 per cent customers of Dinesh garments. Only 14.04 per cent customer opined that prices of Dinesh products were high as compared to competitors, which was the main reason that influenced its popularity and 8.77 per cent customers opined that most of the customers do not know about this product. That means lack of knowledge about the product. And 10.53 per cent customers opined that it was due to other reasons the product was not accepted. They specified that Dinesh brand creates a negative feeling in their mind as it was a beedi brand.

Conclusions and suggestions

The present paper is focused on the products of three units of the society viz foods, umbrella and garments. An attempt is made to analysis the perception of customers towards the diversified products. In order to identify customers perception about Dinesh products sufficient information were collected from the

customers and were analysed using statistical tools and was found that the main factors that attracted the customers towards dinesh products was its price and quality and main drawback of the society was the lack of proper advertisement for their products. If the society takes necessary steps to promote the products it will lead to success.

By fixing the prices a bit lesser than competitors and providing some attractive offers for a short period and giving more advertisement to all products in medias will help to increase the sales. Only by providing advertisement in Medias customers will be aware about the products, especially in case of food products and umbrella.

Though Dinesh brand name is of very high quality and as it is derived from the brand of Dinesh beedi, sophisticated consumers may not be attracted by the conventional brand name of beedi. Therefore the society may think of giving new brand name or other alternative to attract high potential customers.

In the initial period the society had provided some promotional offers to their customers such as coupons, lucky draw etc, but at present no such offers are providing. The society has to continue these offers throughout to capture the attention of their customers.

Company should adopt discriminative pricing policy in such a way that the places having high demand should be priced less and vice versa. Similarly pricing policy adopted by competitors of respective line of products should also be considered.

References

- Jackson, Sherri L, Research Methods and Statistics, Wadsworth/ Thomson Learning, USA, 2003.
- Jain, Gopal Lal, Research Methodology Tools and Techniques, Mangal Deep Publications, 2003.
- Kothari, C.R., Research Methodology Methods and Techniques, New Age International Publishing House, New Delhi, 2009.
- Kotler, Philip, Marketing Management, Analysis, Planning, Implementation and Control, (ninth edition), Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi, 1997.
- Krishnaswamy, O.R. and Obul Reddy D, Research Methodology and Statistical Tools, Himalaya Publications, Mumbai, 2009.
- Kumar, Ranjit, Research Methodology, Sage Publications, 2010.
- Marshall, Greg W and Mark W Johnston, Marketing Management, McGraw Hills Publishing Company, 2010

- Anoop, C.M, 'Consumer awareness and market potentiality of Dinesh Food Products with respect to Kannur District', project report, Bharathair University, 2011
- Larish, K.C, "The attitude and preference of retailers and end users of Dinesh Food Products", Project Report, Bharathair University, 2011.

